

EUROPEAN RADIOISOTOPE DYNAMIC GENERATOR FOR LUNAR NIGHT SURVIVAL AND OPERATIONS. M. Ščepanskis¹ and J. Priede², ¹Deep Space Energy SIA (Kapseļu iela 25A-1, Rīga, LV-1046 Latvia, mihails@deepspaceenergy.space), ²Deep Space Energy Limited (199 Field End Road, C/O Lotuswise, Eastcote, Pinner, Middlesex, England, HA5 1QZ United Kingdom, janis@deepspaceenergy.space).

Introduction: The presentation addresses the critical need to ensure lunar night survival for scouting and prospecting rovers during robotic Moon exploration in the 2030s, including potential operations in permanently shadowed regions. Small rovers require at least 15 kWh to survive the 14-day lunar night, which would demand roughly 100 kg of Li-Ion batteries — nearly the entire rover mass. In contrast, a 45 W-electric (W-e) Radioisotope Power System (RPS) can efficiently meet this energy requirement. Historically, 70 W-e SNAP-27 Radioisotope Thermoelectric Generators (RTGs) powered Apollo Lunar Surface Experiments Packages (ALSEP) through lunar nights.

Today, global limitations in radioisotope production present a significant challenge. Plutonium-238, long used for deep-space and surface missions, is no longer available because its supply was tied to the U.S. nuclear weapons program. New opportunities are now emerging to establish sustainable and scalable civil RPS production. This approach relies on two complementary technologies: sourcing radioisotope fuel from spent nuclear fuel, particularly americium-241 (Am-241) recovered from aged uranium-plutonium products post-PUREX reprocessing in the UK and France, and dynamic heat-to-electric conversion, which reduces fuel consumption per W-e by up to fivefold compared to classical RTGs. Current Am-241 production is limited to approximately 10 kg of oxide per year in the mid-2030s, equivalent to about 2 kW of thermal output per year. With conventional RTGs operating at 5% conversion efficiency, this would generate only about 100 W-e.

NASA previously considered free-piston Stirling designs to increase conversion efficiency, but moving-part reliability concerns prevented flight testing. Now, under contract from the European Space Agency (ESA), Deep Space Energy (DSE) proposes an enhanced single-piston Radioisotope Thermo-Acoustic Linear Induction Generator (RTALIG), which promises 25% conversion efficiency and reduces fuel mass fivefold relative to classical RTGs. Combined with Am-241 sourcing, these technologies enable scalable RPS production and ensure lunar night survival for small rovers in the 2030s.

The technology development: By the end of 2024, DSE completed its ESA design contract. Two converters mounted on opposite sides of a 200 W-th Am-241 Large Radioisotope Heat Unit (LRHU) are designed to deliver approximately 50 W-e, with the system intended for modular scaling. DSE also developed semi-analytical and numerical models to

serve as a digital twin of the RTALIG system. In May 2025, the company demonstrated a TRL 3 experimental proof-of-concept, optimizing the converters for the given heat source. The model assumed a 200 W-th Am-241 target, a two-converter design, hot and cold ends at 680 and 80 °C, and helium as the working fluid, projecting a conversion efficiency of 25.4% and a total mass of 21.8 kg, corresponding to 2.3 W-e/kg (excluding radiator, power management unit, and spacecraft connection) [1].

At the end of 2024, DSE finished the design contract with the European Space Agency (ESA). As demonstrated below, 2 converters at the opposite sides of the 200 W-th European Am-241 Large Radioisotope Heat Unit (LRHU) are designed to deliver approximately 50 W-e. The system is intended to be designed for modular scaling.

Now, the DSE team is progressing toward the TRL4 conversion efficiency demonstration scheduled in May 2026 and marking the next milestone for the technology development.

Scalability and possible impact: RTALIG is being developed as a multi-mission RDG, with primary focus on ESA deep-space science missions requiring long-lasting, maintenance-free operation, and lunar surface missions that demand survival through 14-day nights and robust operation in permanently shadowed craters. With current and foreseen Am-241 production, Europe faces a significant shortfall for planned missions. Classical RTGs with 5% conversion efficiency would require 200 g of Am-241 per W-e, whereas RDG with 25% efficiency needs only 40 g per W-e. For lunar surface operations, a 50 W-e RTALIG would generate 16.8 kWh over a 14-day night, achieving a mass-specific energy of 770 Wh/kg—more than twice the energy density of conventional batteries.

References:

[1] Ščepanskis M. (2025) *NETS 2025*, 275.